

UNDERSTANDING THE EXPERIENCES AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF ADOLESCENTS WHOSE PARENTS REMARRY AFTER DIVORCE

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Abstract

The study was conducted to examine the experiences and quality of life the children have whose parent decides to remarry after they are divorced, irrespective of whether the custodian parent is remarrying, or the non-custodian one. The main goals of the study are; to understand how the parent's decision of getting married again affects their child's mental health, the possible struggles the child goes through during this time, how it affects their relations with their custodian and non-custodian parents, and to what extent the child is able to come to terms and cope with the situation and who does the child blame for their broken family and who helps them throughout. Interviews of 10 such children; whose age ranged from 10 to 19 years, was conducted through a self-constructed interview questionnaire, along with a form that had their consent for the interview. By choosing the targeted sample size of 10 children who agreed and signed the consent form to be interviewed. Due to the SARS-CoV-1 pandemic and the restrictions that are associated with it, the interviews were conducted online, and all these interviews were transcribed to find out the themes. Major themes were derived from the data collected. The data was thoroughly analyzed after reading and reviewing the interviews, and the objective of the research was achieved; the parental decision of remarriage is a major event in the adolescent's life and has a great impact of the child's mental health, lifestyle and their perspective towards marriage. The research also concluded all the emotions, experiences, and hardships that these adolescents experience and the significance of age in this aspect was also seen, as adolescence is an extremely vulnerable stage in every human's life.

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Introduction

Divorce is the process of ending a marriage; when two partners mutually decide to not to live together anymore. There is no precise or exact definition of divorce as it can be described in many ways. According to the Oxford Sociology Dictionary (1994), the definition of divorce is 'the legal dissolution of marriage'. If, at the time of divorce, a couple has one or more children, the issue of 'child custody' takes place. Child custody is of two kinds, legal and physical. The legal custodian is the parent who gets to be the child's decision maker; the parent who makes important decisions for the child, while the physical custodian is the parent with whom the child lives with. More often than not, one parent gets to be both, the legal and the physical custodian. It is important to mention though that legal custody can be joint as well. Both the parents can share the responsibility of making important education-related, health and welfare decisions of their child. This research did not discriminate between the remarriage of custodian and the non-custodian parent, either situation was acceptable.

Remarriage is a marriage that takes place once the previous marriage has been nullified. It is different from a second marriage, as the second marriage can take place while the first marriage is still intact, something that is seen in polygamy. Polygamous relations are heavily linked with religious and social norms, for example, Islam is a religion that allows the man to have up to 4 wives at one time, while in Hinduism, only one wife is allowed and a polygamous Hindu marriage is null and void. It is important to clarify that in this research, we have only looked into remarriage, not second (or third, or fourth) marriage.

This study discussed how important it is to keep in mind the damage a divorce can cause when either of the parent decides to go for a step family environment for their child. This can go either of two ways. The word divorce can either be a blessing for someone who has had a very bad home environment. This can be in the form of everyday fights and arguments between the parents and a child who has witnessed an abusive relationship. The child might not want to go through this pain everyday so, in this situation, ending it all at once might sound like a better idea. It is not only two individuals who decide to end their marriage, it is more than that. If a couple has a child, they should thoroughly consider their child's future, the choice to choose the custodian parent with obviously mutual agreement of the custodian parent as well as the child, mental well-being, the child's stance on the second marriage, if he is willing to move in with the step family or not before finalizing their divorce and should try and exhaust all possible ways of fixing their relationship before eventually ending it if not for themselves for the sake of their child's future.

It might be the worst feeling for the adolescent, who was close to both the parents and they decide to go for a divorce due to any differences in their relationship. It is parents' responsibility to fully prepare the child for his or her future when things won't be the same anymore and they should realize that the child might not be at an age where he or she can handle the news. The child, if he is told to stay away from one of his/her parent or he might as well have to adjust in a step family, so it's easier for the child to handle the situation and if not the parent should wait for as long as required before they think that their child will be able to deal with the news and the consequent change in the family dynamic.

The topic of 'Divorce' has already been thoroughly looked into in many researches. According to American Psychological Association, APA, between 40-50% of marriages end up in divorce in the USA, with a general global trend of marriages ending up in divorce on the rise. Numerous researches have talked about the well-being of couples after the divorce,

or even of the impact of the divorce on the couple's children. However, there are almost no researches to be found when it comes to the well-being of children, the perspective and outlook on life and the experiences of children who go through it, there are almost no researches on how the child copes up and deals with the situation late in their life, what do they have to say to the others who are in the similar situation and also about the ways they cope up, who helps them through the process and how they feel about both of their parents, the child whose parents are divorced and then either of the parent ends up remarrying. Thus, I would like to look into this topic and base my research on the experience of parent re-marriage on the children, to be able to find out more about the effects the lifestyle of the children, as it is a time when children are not only losing their familiar family structure and coming to terms with that, but then also have to try and come to terms with the addition of somebody new, as a step-parent role, without having much of a say in it. They may find it hard to accept the new person, and depending on their age and maturity level, might not be well positioned in coming to terms with it. The World Health Organization, WHO, describes adolescents as individuals in the 10 - 19 age group. This encompasses the children's pubertal age, as well as their teens and is a time period in which the children are already going through psychological complexities and are forming their personalities, and are most likely to be dealing with other problems like bullying, body dimorphic disorder, generalized anxiety, social phobias etc. The presence of a step-parent may accentuate the child's loss of actual parent, provoke a feeling of competition for the remaining parent and may elicit conflicts in loyalty. This is why I believe that more research needs to be done on this topic and through my research, I will look into it in detail.

Research Questions

- Q1) How does remarriage of a parent after divorce effect the child?
- Q2) How do their experiences mold them to be able to cope with their situation?
- Q3) Are adolescents more effected by step parents than children or adults?
- Q4) How do these children view their life after their parents decide to remarry?

Research Objectives

The aim of this research is to examine the experiences and quality of life of the children whose parents decide to go for second marriage, this study will mainly look at a particular age group of children 10 to 19 years old and their mental well-being, experiences after either one of their parent remarries leaving behind the biological parent and acceptance of step family sometimes leaving the child in conflict and depression.

According to Women's foundation (2007) says that a best age to teach self-esteem to a child is between the ages of nine to thirteen so it might as well effect the self-esteem of child.

Rationale

Many of these researches are conducted on the mental health and struggles that a family faces once either one of the parent decides to remarry. These researches talk about the relationship and bond between the step parents and step siblings. These researches also include how second marriages do not work out due to the family's struggle to bond with step relations. There are only a few studies that focus on the mental health, everyday life and their experiences regarding the whole situation of children when they have to adjust with step parents etc. Here, my research is particularly focusing on the experiences of adolescents as this particular age group has not been discussed enough regarding the remarriage of parents.

Literature Review

Jill Matthews Thies MSW in his paper entitled “Beyond divorce: The impact of remarriage on children” (Thies, 1977) explains the impact of remarriage by parents on the mental health of their children. He tries to understand the implications of the changes that include the structural changes between living in a nuclear family towards either living with a single parent and living with both of them simultaneously.

The paper looks at the aspect of processing the grief that includes the loss of parents, and notices that grief is already there and is not processed completely similarly with the idea of loss, while the changes come to be. However, the idea of remarriage also changes the child’s mentality of family hood completely. The paper argues that the loss of natural parents for the child is incomparable. While the sources of love and affection are always present in society, the child lingers for the affection and love between their natural parents, and for them as well. The idea of remarriage does not settle well in the mind of the child, hence they have to constantly navigate between the family structures, where they encounter different forms of ideals, emotions, and sensitivities. These sensitivities and experiences of the child manifest later on in life, in how they view and understand their new family life around them. Similarly, this aspect also manifests in how they view their own personal relationship with other people. This is largely dictated by why and on what terms their parents divorced, and also crucially on the beyond-divorce period experiences of remarriage of the child.

Marlin (2019) in her research mentioned how children feel when their parents are divorced. She highlighted teenagers in particular, mentioning how they get angry when their parents decide to divorce. They usually blame one parent for it. She also mentioned about the possible mental disorders in children due to divorce like adjustment disorder etc.

Another research done by Anderson (2014) has talked about the effects of divorce on the health of children. He talks about how divorce has long term effects on children who never really fully recover and remembers their natural parents and their natural family dynamics even later on in their lives, especially on recurring events and occasions.

A study done in Michigan University by Elyse A. Jennings has discussed the impact of the gender of the child on their relationship with their parents after they are divorced. It concludes that male children are more affected by the divorces than female children are. A study done in 2017 by American study of pederasts, says that a child feels guilt if he or she is bonding with the new parent. This is because he feels that he is disrespecting the other parent. The child also feels that he or she might lose the attention of their parent who is remarrying. This makes the child feel awkward and he or she finds it hard to accept the new family dynamic which can be two fathers or two mothers as well.

Some children might compare their step parent with their real parent so it is to be expected the children will need time to mentally adjust to and accept the new relationship. All children are at different levels of maturity though, and deal with such situations differently. Some children might take it very seriously, and it may take a toll on their mental health for which they would require psychological help and support. It is already very hard to get along with or to accept the step family or a step parent for a child, but it is even harder for a child in his adolescence. A study done in 2006 says that there are always stereotypic phrases used for a step parent, for example, that he or she is selfish or mean. Even the step parent uses stereotypical phrases for their step children; such as labelling the step child ‘spoilt’. This is usually both ways though and makes the situation quite tricky for the parent who decided to remarry.

Another research mentions that remarrying usually occurs when the child is already in grief because of the divorce, and that makes it even harder for the child to accept the new parent. It is also a cause of conflict in loyalty for the child, as he or she may believe that their parent (whoever remarried) was never loyal to them (Jill Matthews, 2009).

Another research (Brain M.D'Onofrio 2011) University of USA'S articles talks about the consequences of the separation or divorce on the quality of life of children, it says that parental separation always turns into a negative outcome, it's always the fights, the conflicts with the authority figures, dropping out of school as well as choosing to go for drugs for relief or increased consumption of alcohol, this all has to do with increased number of depression, low self-esteem, emotional distress among the children who go through such situations, it also mentions that this all depends on the magnitude of effect on the children it's not always the same for all, it varies from children to children and situation to situation.

In another study, concluded in 2017 in the Indian Journal of Psychology Med, a comparative study was done to compare whether the child was better off with a step parent or a single parent. It was noticed that the child with single parent had reported less physical abuse compared to the one living with step family. Almost two-thirds of the children reported physical abuse and almost 71% had reported some sort of a mental disorder in either one or two of the siblings, thus proving, that the family structure significantly effects the mental health of a child.

Divorce, itself, is a world shattering experience for a child. Younger children are usually confused by the concept of divorce, as they do not see their parent's relationship as an individual relationship where they can simply just decide to not live together as one united family anymore. In a study, loss of a parent due to divorce was compared with the loss of death for the children. The results mentioned that the children feel abandoned and they find it very hard to accept the new family dynamics, and having to only meet the non-custodial parent briefly, especially if they are attached to them. In the same research, it was advised that the child should be properly counselled by the parents, or even just one parent, regarding the concept and intricacies of a divorce, at an age where he or she can fully comprehend its meaning and consequences. This usually goes a long way in ensuring the child's psychological well-being.

A study was published in Berlin in 1995 by John Wiley, in which the mental health of adults was measured whose parents were divorced. A sample of children age 7, 11, 13 and 23 was taken by interviews. It showed that adults aged 23 were effected the most when compared to the rest of the children. There was a negative effect on the mental health of these children in the long term, while also considering the child's academic performance, emotional problems and also their socio-economic factors. Adults aged 23 showed the score above the clinical cutoff of Malaise inventory went from 8% to 11% that showed that serious emotional disorders had increased after the divorce of the parents. In some ways, this study is similar to the study that I am conducting but it does not cover the aspect of remarriage of a parent after the divorce. This research has instead focused on the impact of divorce on different age groups.

In an article by Virginia Gilbert, it was mentioned that second marriages are more likely to end than first marriages. This is because divorce is not as big a deal anymore, as it was the first time. A person already gone through a divorce is more likely to have a divorce if he's not happy, than a person who is unhappy in his intact first marriage only. Another major reason for the second marriage ending was mentioned to be that some step parents

don't bond well with the step children, be it due to lack of effort or otherwise, and this gives the other partner a reason to end the marriage as they don't see any progress towards a potential happy family life ahead.

Aaron Anderson talks about the struggles of managing two families. When a partner brings his children from the previous marriage, they expect their new parent to not only manage the new family, but also the children from the previous marriage, making two families. This could result in the new couple not having time for each other, as the responsibilities are doubled, which just makes the situation difficult for everybody involved.

In the article *The Impact of Divorce on Adolescents*, published in August 2020 by Yael Klein in *Evolve*, the exceptional mental health treatment that is, the Teens Rehab Center, a few things are considered that effect the adolescents after their parents' divorce. According to a study, adolescents show increased levels of depression and anxiety, even after 10 years of parental divorce. These adolescents show feelings of grief and sadness. The study also shows that these children are more likely to have decreased stability in their own marriages. It also mentioned that that was because of a few factors and age was one of the most important ones as according to Yael Klein, the effects of divorce varied with the age of the children.

It was mentioned by Dr. Carl Pickhardt, that adolescents are in the detachment phase where they show more aggressive responses. He also mentioned that a child whose parents are divorced holds on to their parent, whereas an adolescent tends to let go off the parent. This increases the independence in an adolescents. In a study published by *Pediatric Child Health* in May-June 2000, an article which promotes mental health of children, it was mentioned that children whose parents are separated are more likely to be dropped out of school. According to the early studies, they are more likely to get in trouble for not following the law and also get into drugs, if compared to the children who live with their biological parents.

A study was conducted where samples of people were taken from the people who were referred to therapy and did not belong to general population. The study showed that a very high proportion of children was negatively affected by parental divorce, and that it lead to the children struggling with their social life. It was also noticed that more than half of the children showed signs of insecurity as well. (Wallenstein and Backless, 2000). In her essay, *Divorce and Remarriage*, Angela Oswalt Morelli looks at the impacts of divorce and subsequent remarriage from the vantage point of a child's emotional understanding of the matter. While most of the researches up till now focus on the family structure and the child's adjustment into his or her new life, Morelli focuses on the tendency of children to view, many times unjustly, themselves to be the cause of this disruption in the family and their struggle with the guilt that follows. Some of the most significant changes that a child deals with post-divorce, Morelli highlights are, moving out of their current home or watching a parent move out, the imbalance in the time spent with either parents, a sense of abandonment and the entire restructuring of events such as family holidays etc. Additionally, she argues about the significance of the parent's role towards their child in the aftermath of a divorce. While it is true that parents go through their own trauma after a divorce and that they need support and means to cope with the situation as well, it is important that they realize that their mental state directly impacts the mental well-being of their children. Hence, the decision of divorce should encompass its effects on the children and how parents intend to deal with those effects.

Morelli further emphasizes on the significance of parents providing the space for their children to talk openly and freely about their emotions regarding the divorce. Also, parents need to open up about the divorce with their children, in order to eliminate any guilt the children might feel. However, one thing needs to be considered. The parents' openness should not detail the intricacies of any affairs that either parent were engaged in. Only information that will help the children process the situation better should be revealed to them.

Research Methodology

Participants

This research includes 10 participants in total through purposive sampling. These adolescents were between the age of 10 to 19 years old, all the participants were chosen at random, no gender or socio economic status was considered in this study, to ensure that the purpose of study only being focused on the mental health of adolescents due to their parents remarriage.

Sources of Data

The study has a self-constructed, structured interview it mostly includes open ended questions. This interview standardize the order of questions that are asked in the interview. By following the pattern we can increase the validity of structured interviews .This was carried out as we could not find any such interview questions available on the internet that could fulfill the purpose of this research study. After thoroughly going through the previous literature review this interview questioner was prepared, keeping in mind the ethical concerns of the study a consent form will also be prepared before interviewing the participants, The form will include the purpose of the study, the form will also include the interview questions to tell the participants if they will be comfortable answering all the questions, this will help us review the responses carefully as the open ended interview questions will provide enough data to base our study on.

Procedure

The study was based on the purposive method of sampling the data. All the participants whose parents remarried were selected after they all agreed to give the interview for the research and would also sign the consent form to make sure they were participating in the research with all their consciousness.

The interviews would mostly be taken online due to the pandemic on voice notes, zoom etc. keeping everyone's preference in mind. Each interview that would be recorded (voice) then transcribed to be published on the research.

Data Analysis

The analysis of the data will be done through the transcribed interviews that will be attached to the research for reference. The data will be thematically analyzed, that is when the data is looked for the important patterns of the data collected. These patterns or themes are used later to comment or address an issue in the research. This is more important than only summarizing the collected data of the research, it makes more sense if the data is thematically analyzed.

The information that will be collected through the interviews will be read over and over again to see the recurring themes in the interviews and those themes can be grouped to analyze the data. Specific statements that would be repeated by the participants in the answers would be viewed carefully to give a more precise discussion of the paper. All the coded and highlighted data would be under specific headings to have a better

understanding of the results further discussed in this research paper.

Ethical Consideration

The participants were informed about the study, it was mentioned that this is only for the academic purpose and they were given free choice whether they want to participate in the study or not. The questioner was made considering the emotions of the child and it was also mentioned if they feel uncomfortable at any point of the interview they may choose to stop answering. The participants were also informed that their names won't be used and anonymity will be maintained throughout the study.

Following is the List of Participants who have Participated in the Research

Participant Number	Gender	Age	Socio economic Class
1	Female	14	Middle Class
2	Female	18	Upper class
3	Female	17	Upper middle class
4	Female	17	Middle Upper Class
5	Male	12	Middle Upper Class
6	Female	16	Middle Upper Class
7	Female	12	Middle Upper Class
8	Male	10	Middle Upper Class
9	Female	18	Middle Class
10	Male	16	Middle Class

Results

After the interviews were transcribed and codes were noticed that led us to general themes were derived from those. In total there were nine themes that were generated which led us to different coping strategies that are three out of the nine themes, these children used to cope up with their situations. Themes have been based on what these children have to go through and what their stance today is and how they copped up with the situation.

Custodian Parent

The most important themes of the interview were based on the point of views of the children about their custodian parent and non-custodian parent, most of the participants were satisfied with their custodian parent even though everyone had their own reasons but most of them agreed that they respected their custodian parent for taking care of them, for making the better decision as the custodian parent would be better able to look after their needs etc. following are the responses of the participants.

“To be honest i don't feel like loving them, there is only respect in my heart and that's all” (P1)

“I really respect her, she didn't marry again and raised 3 kids.” (P2)

“Is very understandable and provides me with everything that I want.” (P5)

“I feel my custodian parent loves me and whatever he is doing is for my good future” (p6).

“ I am satisfied with my life with this parent so I respect their decision of securing my future by choosing the right custodian parent for me” (p10)

“I was happy and attached to custodian parent and more custodian parent” (p9)

Non Custodian

Another very important theme in which most of the participants were of the view that the non-custodian parents were either happy without them or did not have a very close relationship with them, most of them also believed that they did not make effort for them, or did not provide them with whatever they needed so they were to stay with their

custodian parent. A lot of people do not stay in touch with their non-custodian parent so they start to believe that they are not needed so they do not care as well. The interview trend showed some very harsh comments against the non-custodian parents as the children were impacted by the decision that they were not living with their non-custodian parent, they have expectations of a better and more understanding relationship with them.

“I think they are greedy because most of the people marry because of the wealth. They are not kids that if someone asks them to marry so they marry without thinking and they know better that they cannot stay with peace with their so cool partner's ex family. They don't know family values. They put poison in our custodial parents. Because of them we spoil our life” (P1)

“I love him but don't have as close relationship as would've liked but wished he would've made more of an effort before/ been more involved in my life” (P2)

“My non-custodial parent is my biological father, I don't live with him.

I think that it was a good decision to leave him. I don't even talk to him now” (P3)

“Couldn't provide me with all the resources that I needed.” (P5)

“I blame my biological father for making our lives a mess. If he was a good husband or father this wouldn't have happened.”(p3)

General Support

Another very important theme was about the support that these adolescents look for when they are in this situation, most of the participants have said that they did not talk to anyone outside the family and the only support system they built later to rely on is their very close relationships like siblings and grandparents most of them were even financially supported either by the grandparents or their fathers, even if the fathers who were not custodian parents they were supporting financially if not emotionally as the results show that these children were not very comfortable talking about their family issues outside the family and none of the participants have had any psychological help even though they were not really doing great mentally so support outside the family about the family matter is still not encouraged like psychological help etc. To cope with such situations is still not very common. Here are a few responses from the participants.

“Yes I did. I started teaching tuition to young students then and so did my elder sister. We refused to take any sort of help from anyone outside the family financially “ (p7)

“Yes. My grandparents and my friends were really helpful and supportive” (p7)

“- I didn't seek support outside the family and it was a personal matter and I couldn't talk to anyone but my siblings. And financially my father was supporting “ (p5)

“financial stress was there like , how it would go if we decide to live with our mom and there was financial stress even then my dad supported us financially “ (p4)

“. No I didn't seek any support” (p2)

“talking to siblings about it and asked a few friends about advice, my grandparents supported us financially “ (p2)

“Um, there were no financial struggles for us and my father was supporting me financially” (p9)

Held Responsible for Divorce

Another similar theme that was found in the interview that most of the participants did blame either themselves or their parents for the whole situation and it can be challenging to get out of that situation easily.

“Yes I blame them sometimes” (P8)

“Yes I did blamed them and even today I do because if they would have tried we would be a happy family.” (P9)

“I used to blame my father and I still blame him” (P6)

“I blame by biological father for making our lives a mess. If he was a good husband or father this wouldn't have happened”. (P3)

“Yes i blame my non-custodial parent for all the shit, but i do not totally blame my non-custodial parent for what happened in my life because they were not interrupted in our family by their own choice obviously our parent give the permission to spoil our life.” (P1)

Current Perspective on Remarrying

Another theme that was derived from the results to find out about their current stance about remarriage or divorce and a second partner if it was important or not, it was noticed that almost everyone was of the view that second marriage is not necessary and if they were ever in the same situation they would never in the first place get divorce and if that's the last thing that is to happen then they were all sure they would not get married after they are divorced once.

“No I don't think it was important because ever since my father remarried he doesn't care about us.” (p6)

“I would not get divorce” (p6)

“no it wasn't important as the step mom is really rude to us “(P8)

“I would never remarry” (P8)

-“I don't think second marriage was important but maybe for them it was for them and I don't have a say in it.”(p5)

“I would make my marriage work for the sake of my children” (p5)

“I think second marriage should never be a option”(p9)

“For me it's not important at all but for my parents it's their decision” (p4)

“I'm not in favor of second marriages but I would leave if not happy” (p3)

“A big No and if you want to marry, have sex, so please keep your kids away from that --- or from that --. Shift your kids to other place far away from them” (p1)

No not at all “(p2)

Coping Strategies

After asking about everyone's coping strategy most of them said that they had tried to do something to keep them busy and not think too much about the problem, even if they did they just talked to their own siblings or close one to keep them sane throughout.

“I tried to keep myself to myself and try not to disturb them or their time or their personal time I have tried to avoid that.”(P9)

“) I started spending a lot of time outside of the house” (P7)

a lot of head that went into it it was very very difficult at first and there as a lot of negative emotional setback and communication between the siblings so it was a lot better then when we talked about . (P4)

Suggestions for Others

Upon asking what they would suggest for others who are going through the same they had a few similar suggestions to give that have been listed below.

“Mind your own business and take each day as it comes stay positive and this was of course life.”(P9)

”I would advise them to not engulf themselves in sorrow. They should become more mature and responsible themselves and if they need help, they should not feel ashamed in seeking for it “(P7)

“- I would advise them not to listen to people's opinions regarding their parents and never blame a single person for the divorce” (P6)

Patients and I had no other choice and I had to deal with the matter very maturely. (P5)

For kids they should not feel the burden that's better for them parents are mature and they know what to do you are the kid in the situation so you should not take too much stress about it and detach from the set boundaries.(P4)

To try their hardest to make efforts with both sides of the family and to reach out to parent if not in contact with them. (P2)

Focus on Studies

Another way most of the participants responded when they were asked how did they cope up with the situations was that many of them said that they started to focus on their studies even more than they used as they thought this would keep them busy and help them become independent.

“I used to study all the time, I could not believe I was competing with my classmates who used to be the position holders” (P10)

I coped with the situation by just accepting the facts and getting busy in my studies (p3)

“I was devastated but soon realized none cares about us so I started to work hard to succeed in studies, that is what could do” (P6)

Single Parent Over Step Family

One very important theme was found from the participants responses where they were asked if it was better off living with a step family or step parent or move in with a single parent, most of the children had answered saying how it gets very difficult to adjust with new family, you almost get to start all over again, there is almost no acceptability of a step child either it just leads to more and more conflicts with step parent as well as the biological parent, therefore its better that you live with a single parent at least you would be able to focus on yourself and not feel unwanted or a burden over someone who might not be willing to live with you either, here are some of the responses.

“: I think it's better to stay with single parent then destroying yourself by moving in step family.” (p1)

“I feel like I don't belong in their lives. So prefer to stay with single parent” (p2)

“ I would choose single parent as step parents attention being diverted because of new commitments, there were many such changes”(p5)

“I believe living with single parent is better “(p8)

“yes I would never ever be in favor of living in step family as it gets hard and starts to affect you mentally so one is better off with a single parent” (p9)

“I would always choose single parent over the step family, they make your life hell and never ever accept you” (p10)

Discussion

This research was significantly able to prove that adolescent's whose parents remarried after they were divorced did face some sort of issues they had experienced life differently and had a lot of regrets and it did leave an impact on them, however they were able to cope up with it with different strategies and their perspective today still remain against the decision of getting married again I god forbid once divorced.

The most important theme that was proved that all of them somehow felt that they all did have respect for their custodial parent for taking their responsibility and looking after them, even if some were not happy with their custody decisions on their parents part

but they still did respect them and did not really have harsh feelings for anyone. This also did make them feel secure and acceptable by them. In the light of another similar research that was mentioned in the literature review by study (2017) Indian J psyche med it is when a child is actually finding it hard to let go of the non-custodial parent and make peace with the custodian parent, it says that it's already very hard for the child to overcome the loss of a parent and adjust to only one parent that's when the child starts to get attached to this parent and only have his attention so they tend to start respecting them for merely what do every day to meet the ends. It also talked about the children's preference of living with a single parent than moving into a step family, it showed how the children felt more secure and there was less physical abuse reported from the children who had been living with single parents rather than with the step family, this was another theme in our research that most of the adolescents chose to stay with the single parent rather than moving in a step family.

Another most important theme that gives us an insight in the minds of the adolescents about their pattern as in who do they think is responsible for the situation that they are in, most of them believe and tend to blame one of the parent about their situation and they think that that one parent is responsible for their mental status today and how they could have made things better but chose not to, how they could have made better decisions to deal with the situation and they see them as the issue and route cause of their issues in their lives. (Marlin, august 06th 2019) shows that these adolescents start to blame one of the parent for the whole situation and have negative thoughts about that one parent who is blamed for the whole situation.

Another study by (Anderson, November 2014) show that these adolescents never fully recover they tend to have some of their parts missing that are essential for the developmental period and in their age they lack that particular attention from their parent, so these adolescents some of them had used very harsh words against their parents or expressed anger towards the situation, in a few responses we also noticed how they still wish they could fix something, these adolescents start to feel neglected by the parent who remarries and start to think that they do not get the same attention, also they feel that the parent that remarries, priorities the new family and children over them and they feel unwanted by their own parent.

(American study of pederasts, 2017) this was about the acceptance of the new parent that their biological get married to, it shows that they are still not over the loss of one of their own parent that they lose due to divorce and then getting themselves to accept someone new is very hard for them, this study shows how it gets very awkward for these children to think of a new parent like having to call two people their father. This is very hard to accept new parents

In the sample it was also very evident that almost all the children wanted to live with a single parent and none chose to move in with the step family irrespective of the custodian parent or non-custodian parent, the children did feel neglected and they felt like they were bothering the step family. Some also mentioned how the attention of their own biological parent changed and it was very unacceptable to deal with everyday situation in the step family so they would rather stay with single parent then move into an already messed up situation, none cared about the financial status of the single parent, almost all of them had an instant instinct to go for a single parent as it was not ideal in any situation to choose to live with the step family.

(By John Wiley in 1995) in Berlin where normal children's mental health was compared to the ones who had been remarried after divorce, the children whose parents decide to remarry always lack some or the other thing in them, they are never able to see themselves as someone complete like the children who live in a stable family, the children who come from a broken family have different issues and only they can relate to like weekly custody, the court decisions and how its not in their control, at least till they are under 18, it's the age where they want attention, they look out for care, love from their family so when they do not get it they start to deviate from the norms etc. hence their comparison cannot be done with the children who have had a fully functioning life all their life.

(In 27th August 2020 by Yael Klein) (The Impact of Divorce on Adolescents) decreased marital stability and sadness etc. in adolescents, this research that is mentioned in my literature review shows the impact of adolescents whose parents were divorced they showed sadness and instability in their marital lives, according my study if we compare the responses, it shows that most of the participants in my research responded to questions asked about their future vision of their married life, most of them, did feel that they would compromise and really make efforts to have a stable married life in future as they did not want their children to go through what they had faced, but that's something one can actually find out when they are already in it hence no conclusion can be made on this particular study from the literature review as yet.

(By Dr Carl Pickhardt) this study that is mentioned in this research's literature review shows that the children whose parents had remarried they are more aggressive. In the responses I got a few of the participants did show anger and aggression even in their interview some of them even went to an extent to use foul language for their parents so it was noticed in most of the participants at some point or the other that they did use an aggressive tone in the interview when asked about a few questions.

(Wallenstein and Backless, 2000) this was a study conducted that showed how the social life of the children whose parents were divorced was effected it also reflected in our research as most of the children said that their friends were their family members and they were close to their siblings or custodian parents, most of them also said that they did not feel like shat=ring their issues with their friends, it means that the children whose parents are divorced they do feel there is something wrong with their family structure and never feel okay to talk to their friends about it, they might not even have such close friends, there might be situations that they would not be able to make friends or socialize as their getting away situation was that they got busy with studying and not focus, none of them really talked about having very good friends to be able to share their experience or generally look back to when needed.

By pediatric child health in (May June 2000) drugs and law issues if not living with biological parent, this study was mentioned as it could be the mechanism for others to use to get away or cope up with their situation. The participants who had responded to this research did not show any sort of coping strategies like taking drugs or getting into bad habits like smoking, most of them used the avoidant mechanism to completely avoid the situation and let it be, some also chose to divert attention towards their studies to keep themselves busy.

(Angela Oswald Morelli guilt) that follows not adjust etc., this study shows how there is guilt in the adolescents whose parents remarry and they do not talk about it freely, yes most of the participants did say that they did not talk to anyone about the situation, it could be a mess, none was really looking to discuss the issue outside the family, if they

asked for support that was only within the family mostly, As far as adjustment is concerned yes, it was mostly the children who were still struggling to come to terms with the fact that they had adjusted with the new family (step family) most of them even mentioned that its better off living with a single biological parent rather than moving in with a parent who had decided to get married again, most of them suggested to live with a single parent rather than living with a step parent as it becomes very hard to adjust with new family.

Limitations

The sample size of the research was not enough to generalize it for all adolescents. We were restricted to take the interviews online due to pandemic so facial expressions etc. , were neglected and it was felt that people just answered the questions for the sake of it as it was a very difficult topic for them to open up about and they had moved on so didn't really care a lot, maybe people did not answer the questions very carefully as they would have, if asked in person. We were not able to take in consideration the socio economic background in our study as again, we were restricted to take the interviews online and it was mostly the people who were privileged enough to have access to the internet, that might affect the results of the study. Results were discussed irrespective of gender consideration there was not equal male to female ratio due to limited people who were willing to be interviewed on such a sensitive topic for them, also family dynamics were not taken in consideration that might vary, this was also from Pakistani peoples point of as all the participants were from Pakistan, so it can also influence our results.

Recommendations

As in regard to this study it is recommended for the adolescents to always look out for help if needed, they should be taking therapy to help them cope with positive strategies to deal with their situation as they might be falling in negative influence or to avoid any sort of negative coping strategies they should consult and see therapist.

Most of these children do not even talk to anyone and let things built up within themselves, as children they are not even aware of the therapy so parents should consider and take these measures for the better mental health and future mental stability of their child. Considering the stigma that is attached to our society about visiting a psychologist or therapist for any matter should be ruled and these children should be given the opportunity to talk and let that negativity out of them so they can better handle their lives in future and that does not affect them in any other way or cause any sort of hindrance in their lives.

Another recommendation would be that the parents should prepare and give time to the children especially in adolescents as they are more sensitive and they do understand the situation if they atr dealt with proper attention at that particular time, if their consent is taken in consideration regarding second marriage as they also now have to accept the new dynamics of the family so it would be really helpful for them to further cope with the situation and they will be at better place mentally f they are already aware.

Conclusion

The research concluded that the adolescents whose parents remarry after they were divorced do have different experiences and their quality of life is disturbed as compared to how it would have been if they would grow up in a normal family, while growing up and they do not grow up in ideal conditions and always wish for a happy family however it was concluded that they do adopt their own coping strategies and their own strong opinion on such situations that does leave an impact on their lives, furthermore a larger sample would

be required to generalize tis for all the adolescents keeping in mind the situations differ from family to family.

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